

APPENDIX Tools reconstructing Microservice Architecture: A Systematic Mapping Study

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Abstract. This is the online appendix for the paper "Tools Reconstructing Microservice Architecture: A Systematic Mapping Study".

Key words: Microservice, Software Architecture, Architectural Reconstruction

A summary of the main properties of discovered tools was given in the main paper. In this Appendix, we include:

- Table 1 - A summary of tools' repository information: its availability, last update month, amount of commits, starts, forks, and contributors as well as the supported language/platform that the tool covers
- Table 2 - A summary of tools' input
- Table 3 - A summary of tools' output, recovery method and purpose, availability of visualization
- Table 4 - For each tool, the paper introducing the tool as well as all papers from the selected ones that cite the tool
- List of all papers collected in the study

Explanations of input and output codifications are given in the main paper.

Table 1. Tools’ repository availability and statistics

Tool name	Repo	License	Last update	Commits	Stars	Forks	Contributors	Supported Platforms
Arcan	✓	Proprietary	N/A (Active)	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	Java, C, C++, C#, Python
ARCHI4MOM	✓	N/A	29.06.2022	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	OpenTracing
Aroma	✓	MIT	17.04.2023	38	N/A	N/A	5	OpenTracing
attack-graph-generator	✓	N/A	28.01.2021	87	24	8	3	Docker
Code2DFD	✓	Apache v2	07.06.2023	2 ¹	2	0	1	Java (Spring)
Decomposer	✓	N/A	20.12.2016	20	3	0	1	Java
IdentificationApproach	✓	N/A	24.01.2022	9	0	N/A	1	Java
ImpactAnalysis	✓	N/A	01.01.2019	N/A ²	N/A ²	N/A ²	N/A ²	Java
istio-log-parser	✓	N/A	26.05.2022	13	0	0	1	Istio
MAIG	-	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	OpenTracing
MicADO	✓	MIT	28.06.2022	9	0	7	1	Any
microART	✓	Academic	17.04.2017	27	11	6	3	Docker
MicroDepGraph	✓	N/A	24.11.2021	49	4	7	2	Java
microFreshener	✓	MIT	03.11.2022	179	12	2	5	Any
Microlyze	✓	N/A	20.07.2018	20	0	0	2	Eureka/Consul, OpenTracing
MicroMiner	✓	MIT	21.11.2020	160	8	2	2	Kubernetes
MAAT	-	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	OpenTracing
microserviceExtraction	✓	Academic	05.02.2020	150	13	7	1	Java
microTOM	✓	MIT	12.01.2023	22	0	0	2	Kubernetes, Kiali
monitoring_ms	✓	N/A	19.08.2018	59	3	2	1	Zuul, Eureka, Docker Swarm
mono2micro (socialsoftw.)	✓	MIT	12.06.2023	609	6	8	12	Java
Mono2Micro (IBM)	✓	Proprietary	N/A (Active)	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	Java
MonoToMicro ([77])	-	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	Java
MS-MDE-RL	✓	GPL v3	05.01.2022	15	0	1	2	Java
MSA-Nose	✓	N/A	12.04.2021	6	2	3	2	Java
MSDesigner	-	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	Java (OO language)
MSExtractor	-	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	Java
Rademacher et al. ([12])	✓	N/A	05.03.2020	1 ¹	0	0	1	Java
De Alwis et al. ([29])	✓	N/A	15.07.2019	1 ¹	1	0	1	Java
Ntentos et al. ([80])	✓	CC BY 4.0	02.02.2021	N/A	N/A	N/A	4	Any
OpenTracingProcessor	✓	MIT	18.07.2019	3	4	0	2	OpenTracing
Prophet	✓	N/A	02.09.2021	208	2	0	6	Java
RAD	✓	N/A	22.01.2021	87	0	1	1	Java, Python
ServiceCutter	✓	Apache v2	27.05.2021	341	66	18	4	Java
Subtype	✓	N/A	01.05.2018	1 ¹	0	2	1	Any
VECROSim	✓	N/A	24.12.2022	31	1	1	1	Kubernetes
VMAMV	✓	N/A	20.01.2022	798	1	0	2	Java

¹ Repository has been migrated without preserving history² Repository does not use git correctly

Table 2. Tools' input

Tool name	Input type	Input format
Arcan	Source	-
ARCHI4MOM	Traces	Jaeger traces
Aroma	Traces	Zipkin Traces
attack-graph-generator	Deployment files	docker-compose.yml
Code2DFD	Source	Git repository
Decomposer	Model-GFS	OpenAPI specification of all methods
IdentificationApproach	Source	-
ImpactAnalysis	Model-GFS	-
istio-log-parser	Traces	Istio logs
MAIG	Traces	Zipkin Traces
MicADO	Traces, Model-MCF	JSON model of the architecture, JSON model of production load
microART	Source, Deployment files, Traces	GitHub repository, Dockerfiles, TcpDump logs
MicroDepGraph	Source	-
microFreshener	Model-GFS	microTOSCA
Microlyze	Traces	Access to Eureka/Consul service discovery, Zipkin traces
MicroMiner	Deployment files	Kubernetes deployment files
MAAT	Traces	Zipkin Traces, Asynchronous call logs
microserviceExtraction	Source	Git repository
microTOM	Deployment files, Traces	Kubernetes deployment files, Kiali interaction graph
monitoring_ms	Traces	Docker-deployed system
mono2micro (socialsoftw.)	Source	-
Mono2Micro (IBM)	Traces	Instrumented traces
MonoToMicro ([77])	Source	-
MS-MDE-RL	Model-GFS	Outputs of MoDisco and ServiceCutter given the source as input
MSA-Nose	Source	-
MSDesigner	Model-MCF	UML class diagram in XML format
MSExtractor	Source	-
Rademacher et al. ([12])	Source	-
De Alwis et al. ([29])	Source, Traces	Java source code, XES-format traces
Ntentos et al. ([80])	Model-MCF	UML Model
OpenTracingProcessor	Traces	Zipkin traces
Prophet	Source	-
RAD	Source	-
ServiceCutter	Model-GFS	ERM model of classes in JSON format, use cases in JSON format
Subtype	Model-GFS	Monolithic call graph (Disco)
VECROSim	Model-MCF	Description of deployment, load, faults and metrics
VMAMV	Source	-

Table 3. Tools’ output and purpose

Tool name	Output	Output sub-category	Output format	Recovery	Tool aims	Vis.
Arcan	Smells, Logical view	-	Web visualization	S	SD	✓
ARCHI4MOM	Operational view	SDG	PCM model	D	MR	✓
Aroma	Operational view	SDG	JSON	D	MR, SD	✓
attack-graph-generator	Health Metrics	Attack graph	JSON	S	VD	✓
Code2DFD	Operational view	Dataflow Diagram	TXT, JSON, Codable Models, PNG	S	MR, VD	✓
Decomposer	Logical view	C2M	TXT	S	M2M	-
IdentificationApproach	Service view	C2M	?	S	M2M	-
ImpactAnalysis	Tests	CRUD tests	?	S	Test generation	✓
istio-log-parser	Service view	SDG	dot graph	D	MR	✓
MAIG	Service view, anti-patterns	SDG, anti-patterns detected	Visualizations	D	MR, P	✓
MicADO	Service view	C2M	JSON	H	MR	✓
microART	Service view	SDG	XMI	H	MR	-
MicroDepGraph	Service view	SDG	Neo4j, GraphML, SVG	S	MR	✓
microFreshener	Service view	SDG	Visualizations	S	SD	✓
Microlyze	Service view	SDG	Visualizations	D	MR	✓
MicroMiner	Service view	SDG	microTOSCA	H	MR	✓
MAAT	Service view	SDG	Visualizations	D	MR, P	✓
microserviceExtraction	Service view	C2M	?	S	M2M	✓
microTOM	Service view	SDG	microTOSCA	H	MR	✓
monitoring_ms	Service view, Health metrics	SDG	?	D	MR, MO	✓
mono2micro (socialsoftw.)	Service view	C2M	JSON	H	M2M	✓
Mono2Micro (IBM)	Service view	C2M	JSON	D	M2M	✓
MonoToMicro ([77])	Service view	C2M	?	S	M2M	-
MS-MDE-RL	Service view	C2M	TXT	S	M2M	✓
MSA-Nose	Smells	-	JSON	S	SD	-
MSDesigner	Service view	C2M	?	S	M2M	✓
MSExtractor	Service view	C2M	?	S	M2M	-
Rademacher et al. ([12])	Domain view Service view Operation view	-	CSV	S	MR	-
De Alwis et al. ([29])	Service view	C2M	?	H	M2M	-
Ntentos et al. ([80])	Refactorings, Violations	Suggested refactorings	?	S	MO	-
OpenTracingProcessor	Service view, Health metrics	SDG	?	D	MR, MO	✓
Prophet	Service view	SDG	Neo4j	S	MR	-
RAD	Service View	SDG, Endpoint access roles	JSON	S	MR, Security analysis	-
ServiceCutter	Service View	C2M	JSON	S	M2M	✓
Subtype	Service View	C2M	?	H	M2M	-
VECROSim	Health Metrics	System response to injected faults	CSV	D	MO	-
VMAMV	Health Metrics	System response to injected faults	OAS, JSON	H	MO	-

Table 4. Tools' introductions and mentions

Tool Name	Introduced	Mentioned
Arcan	[1]	[7],[24],[25],[59],[84],[85]
ARCHI4MOM	[21]	None
Aroma	[59]	[59]
attack-graph-generator	[22]	[27],[60],[69],[70],[76],[91]
Code2DFD	[5]	None ¹
Decomposer	[2]	[7],[8],[9],[13],[14],[20],[28],[40],[42],[43],[46],[50],[53],[58],[66],[71],[77],[85],[94]
IdentificationApproach	[52]	None
ImpactAnalysis	[19]	None
istio-log-parser	[90]	[60]
MAAT	[37]	[40],[49],[59],[89]
MAIG	[89]	[39]
MicADO	[4]	[7],[8],[28],[29],[43]
microART	[55]	[7],[12],[15],[21],[35],[56],[59],[62],[68],[80],[84],[86]
MicroDepGraph	[63]	[10],[60],[75],[88],[89],[5]
microFreshener	[84]	[59],[68],[71],[76],[5]
Microlyze	[56]	[21],[49],[59],[71]
MicroMiner	[62]	[68],[84],[87]
microserviceExtractor	[41]	[7],[8],[9],[11],[13],[14],[16],[17],[18],[20],[31],[46],[50],[43],[66],[67]
microTOM	[68]	None
monitoring.ms	[65]	[23],[54]
mono2micro (socialsoftw.)	[43]	[7],[8],[34],[48],[52],[53],[61]
Mono2Micro (IBM)	[66],[67]	[11],[14],[31],[46],[50],[94]
MonoToMicro	[77]	[7],[52]
MS-MDE-RL	[42]	None
MSA-Nose	[25]	[24],[49],[60],[90]
MSDesigner	[26]	None
MSExtractor	[6]	[11],[71]
Rademacher et al.	[12]	[49],[60],[62],[68],[69],[70],[76],[84],[90],[91]
De Alwis et al.	[29]	None
Ntentos et al.	[80]	None
OpenTracingProcessor	[23]	None
Prophet	[91]	[60],[69],[70],[76],[5]
RAD	[69]	[60]
ServiceCutter	[82]	[7],[8],[9],[10],[13],[14],[26],[28],[31],[34],[38],[41],[42],[48],[44],[45],[46],[48],[50],[57],[53],[58],[61],[66],[81],[85],[94]
Subtype	[3]	[7],[10],[29],[45],[53],[66],[67]
VECROSim	[92]	None
VMAMV	[93]	[76],[5]

¹ The tool and respective paper were published after we performed the literature search and were included by 'Snowballing of known sources'

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